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СОВЕРШИЛ ВСЕ ВОЗМОЖНЫЕ ОШИБКИ
В ОЧЕНЬ УЗКОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ.*

Нильс Бор

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PROMISING SOLUTIONS TO STRATEGIC ISSUES IN THE FIELD OF CYBERSECURITY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article covers the essence of the Cybersecurity Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, divides the digitalization of society into stages, and provides conclusions about Uzbekistan's capabilities and prospects in cybersecurity.

Keywords: Cyber policy, Cybersecurity Center, Safe City, National segment, information infrastructure, cybersecurity sector.

The issue of combating cyber threats is increasingly rising to the level of state policy in our country. In today's era of highly developed information technologies, a number of legal and practical works are being carried out to create a secure information environment, work on the basis of protected systems, and develop a culture among people of the correct use of electronic systems of the state, state bodies, organizations, and institutions. In particular, the importance of protecting young people, who are the leaders of tomorrow, from virtual threats and forming «virtual morality» in young people is emphasized.

The following regulatory documents adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan after independence serve as the legal basis for improving the field of cybersecurity. Laws adopted by the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1060-XII dated 06.05.1994 «On the legal protection of programs and databases created for electronic computers», No. 611-II dated 29.04.2004 «On electronic document management», No. 560-II dated 11.12.2003 «On informatization», No. O'RQ-764 dated April 15, 2022 «On cybersecurity»; Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-3080 dated 30.05.2002 «On further development of computerization and introduction of information and communication technologies», No. PQ-91 dated 02.06.2005 «On improving the system of personnel training in the field of information technologies», No. PQ-614 dated 03.04.2007 «On measures to organize cryptographic protection of information in the Republic of Uzbekistan», No. PQ-4024 dated 21.11.2018 «On measures to improve the system of control over the

introduction of information technologies and communications, their protection», No. PQ-3549 dated 19.02.2018 «On organization of the activities of the Ministry for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On», «On measures to digitize the activities of judicial authorities» dated 03.09.2020 No. PQ-4818, On measures to approve the strategy «Digital Uzbekistan – 2030» and measures for its effective implementation dated 05.10.2020 No. PF-6079, and other regulatory documents are among them. As noted in the «Declaration of Cybersecurity Independence», a legal framework has been created for managing cyberspace in Uzbekistan. The author of the «Declaration of Cybersecurity Independence» John Perry Barlow noted that the network is a purely self-regulating system, not subject to any mandatory regulation, and it should be built only in accordance with moral, but legal laws [1]. There are enough problems in the ethical and technical aspects of ensuring cybersecurity. The activities of the Cybersecurity Center, as one of the main entities in the technical provision of cybersecurity, are of great importance. The establishment of the Cybersecurity Center consists of 4 stages.

Stage 1. The state institution «Center for Ensuring Information Security» under the Ministry of Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan began its activities as a non-profit organization in the form of a state institution operating in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-1989 dated June 27, 2013 «On measures for further development of the National Information and Communications System of the Republic of Uzbekistan» and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 250 dated September 16, 2013 «On measures for organizing the activities of the Center for Developing the „Electronic Government“ System and the Center for Ensuring Information Security under the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Communications, Informatization and Telecommunication Technologies».

Stage 2. In order to implement the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3245 dated August 29, 2017 «On measures to further improve the project management system in the field of information and communication technologies» and to strengthen measures aimed at ensuring information and public security, as well as law and order using modern technologies, and to ensure the timely and high-quality implementation of the project to create a unified hardware and software complex «Safe City», by the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers, the Information Security Center of the Ministry for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan was reorganized into the Center for Assistance in Ensuring Information Security and Public Order of the Ministry for the Development

of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Stage 3. The State Inspectorate of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Supervision in the Field of Informatization and Telecommunications operated as an organization in the form of a state unitary enterprise under the name of the State Unitary Enterprise «Technical Assistance Center» in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4024 dated November 21, 2018 «On measures to improve the system of control over the introduction of information technologies and communications, their protection».

Stage 4. The Cybersecurity Center operates under the name of the State Unitary Enterprise in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4452 dated September 14, 2019 «On additional measures to improve the system of control over the introduction of information technologies and communications, their protection».

The main tasks of the center are as follows [2]:

- Develop recommendations and proposals for the rapid adoption of effective organizational and software-technical solutions that will ensure the collection, analysis and consolidation of information on current threats to information security, and the prevention of illegal access to information systems, resources and databases of state bodies and organizations;

- Cooperate with telecommunications network operators and providers, law enforcement agencies in analyzing and identifying lawbreakers, methods and tools used to commit unauthorized or disruptive actions in the information space;

- Conducting attestation, examination and certification of hardware and software products, information and communication technologies, telecommunications equipment and other technical means in informatization facilities (except for state secrets);

- Assist in the development and implementation of information security policies for information systems and resources of state bodies and organizations;

- Develop proposals to improve the regulatory and legal framework in the field of ensuring information security of state information systems and resources, as well as the national segment of the Internet;

- Timely notification of national Internet users about emerging threats to information security in the national segment of the Internet, as well as provision of consulting services on information protection.

Unfortunately, as is the case all over the world, security in Uzbekistan is not fully effective. It is necessary to use a comprehensive approach, which includes the development and implementation of appropriate legal, organizational, technical and other measures to ensure information and cybersecurity [3].

In this regard, some of the current external and internal threats that negatively affect the national interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of cybersecurity include the following:

- the growth of cross-border crime using information and communication technologies against information systems and resources of the public and private sectors, as well as telecommunications networks and critical information infrastructure. Cyberspace, due to its asymmetric nature and potential severity, has become a key topic of national security interests [4]. While in traditional wars, states have clearly defined borders and are able to determine the trajectory of future actions, cross-border threats in cyberspace cannot be predicted in advance;

- in the context of the growing technological gap between developed countries, our republic is increasingly dependent on the use of foreign technologies and programs to protect its information systems and resources, as well as critical information infrastructure. We are disclosing important information as a result of our use of technologies from other countries. The effective functioning of a person, team, and organization largely depends on the level of ownership of information and the ability to use it effectively [5]. This process sets the task for society to develop national technologies and programs with strong protection;

- The problem of the lack of cybersecurity tools, techniques, programs and devices developed by local manufacturers in the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure cybersecurity. It is worth noting that the absence of a single reputable company in Uzbekistan that develops software for electronic devices negatively affects the activities of higher educational institutions specializing in ICT;

- the level of informatization of state and economic management bodies, local government bodies (hereinafter referred to as state agencies) of the republic lags behind developed countries of the world. According to reports from the Info@mixmode.ai website, Uzbekistan ranks 58th in the international cybersecurity index for 2024 [6], which is not encouraging; kiberjinoatchilik hamjamiyatlari, xalqaro ekstremistik, terroristik va boshqa jinoiy guruh va tashkilotlarning kibermakondagi faoliyatining keskinlashuvi;

- the continued use of outdated, morally and technically obsolete devices, equipment, and unlicensed software in the creation and development of our republic's important information infrastructure, information systems and resources, and telecommunications networks;

- poor coordination of the activities of state agencies to strengthen the cybersecurity of our country and insufficient financial support for measures aimed at protecting cyberspace;

- the weakness of the current regulatory and legal framework regulating issues of ensuring cybersecurity of modern ICTs, and the weak implementation of international standardization issues;

- Examples include the lack of qualified specialists in the field of cybersecurity, the inadequate training and retraining system in this area, and a number of other negative factors.

The following are a number of pressing issues in this area that await resolution:

- the implementation issues (cybersecurity strategy) based on a single principle and approach to ensuring sustainable cybersecurity at the republican level still remain open. The development of a cybersecurity strategy is a requirement of the time to create a systematic mechanism for ensuring cybersecurity across the country. The cybersecurity strategies of 102 countries were published on the website of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) [7]. Among the CIS countries, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, the Russian Federation, and Kazakhstan are included in this list. Unfortunately, Uzbekistan is included in this list among the countries that do not have a cybersecurity strategy;

- the issue of developing a document defining important regulatory and legal frameworks that define a unified approach to cybersecurity issues, namely the Concept of Ensuring Cybersecurity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, has not been brought to its logical conclusion;

- the priority of tasks to strengthen the role and place of state administration bodies in ensuring the cybersecurity of critical information infrastructures remains partially ignored by the leadership of these bodies;

- the secrecy of a number of regulatory and legal acts on the requirements for ensuring cybersecurity of informatization and critical information infrastructure facilities (resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan — adopted under the symbol (KhDFU). This prevented the transfer of requirements for attestation of informatization facilities and cybersecurity to non-governmental organizations — developers and suppliers of software products);

- the number of capable specialists who can accurately and precisely analyze the identified shortcomings in information systems and resource owners (organizations) does not meet the requirements of the time;

- the timely and high-quality elimination of vulnerabilities identified by their owners during the examination of information systems and resources of state bodies and organizations for compliance with cybersecurity requirements is unsatisfactory;

- the material and technical support allocated to cybersecurity is insufficient to fully implement the current situation in the field and the set tasks;

- vulnerabilities identified in connection with a cybersecurity incident, IP address information, and information necessary for analyzing cybersecurity incidents are not fully and timely provided to the authorized body.

In turn, the elimination of the above-mentioned negative factors requires the positive resolution of the following tasks. In particular:

- To develop and approve the Cybersecurity Concept for 2024–2030 in order to ensure the cybersecurity of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- Bringing to a logical conclusion the formation of a set of subordinate legal and regulatory documents aimed at ensuring the direct implementation of the requirements of the Law of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-764 «On Cybersecurity» dated April 15, 2022;

- Development of a regulatory legal act regulating the work with confidential information and ensuring its security at informatization facilities of the Republic of Uzbekistan (with the exception of state secrets);

- ensuring the openness of documents, taking into account the confidentiality level (XDFU) of a number of regulatory and legal documents on the requirements for ensuring informatization and cybersecurity of critical information infrastructure facilities;

- strengthening the role and place of heads of state administration bodies in ensuring the cybersecurity of critical information infrastructures;

- taking legal, technical, and organizational measures on cybersecurity, monitoring the development of cybersecurity capacity and establishing international cooperation agreements on this issue, and conducting planned cybersecurity audits as part of measures to ensure information and cybersecurity in government bodies and organizations;

- It is necessary to establish liability for new types of crimes committed against or using information and communication technologies, while reviewing the list of offenses and crimes related to information technologies, which fully meet today's requirements.

At the same time, in order to ensure the effectiveness of the work being carried out in the field of cybersecurity:

- it is necessary to continuously improve the skills of information and cybersecurity specialists and to establish scientifically based requirements for them;

- each developed or under development information system or resource should avoid repeating the shortcomings identified in previous projects;

- it is necessary to develop, approve and consistently implement regulatory and legal documents on the requirements for ensuring the cybersecurity of state information systems and resources, the prevention of information and cybersecurity incidents and accidents, taking measures against them, and eliminating the consequences of incidents.

In addition, taking into account the above, we consider it appropriate to implement the following measures aimed at improving the state of information and cybersecurity in the information systems and resources of state and economic management bodies, local government bodies, and

important information infrastructure facilities, and further increasing the effectiveness of the reforms being implemented in the field.

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